

design with 4 replications of 3 spacings (10- × 10-cm, 15- × 10-cm, and 20- × 10-m) and 3 basal N rates: recommended dose, 50 kg N/ha; 25% more N, 62.5 kg N/ha; and 50% more N, 75 kg N/ha. All treatments were topdressed with urea at 50 kg N/ha in 2 splits at 15-d intervals.

Soil was clay loam with pH 7.5, low available N, and medium P and K.

Planting aged seedlings at close spacing did not significantly increase yield. Basal application of 75 kg N/ha gave significantly higher yield. Interactions between spacing and N application rates were

significant. At 10- × 10-cm spacing, there was no significant yield difference between N application rates, but at 15- × 10-cm and 20- × 10-cm, yield increased significantly with more N. The 20- × 10-cm spacing and basal 75 kg N/ha gave the highest yield (see table). □

Stubble management for summer lowland rice

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We evaluated stubble management to reduce the required fertilizer application for lowland rice in Jan-Feb 1982-84 at TNAU. Co 43 was planted the first season and IR20 the second. The soil was a clay loam with pH 8.0-8.5 (1:2.5 soil water ratio). Temperature varied from 17°C to 30°C during the cropping season.

N content of the stubble was 0.4-0.5% by weight. Stubbles of different heights were left in the field after harvest and plow-incorporated, then 22 kg P as powdered rock phosphate and 42 kg K as muriate of potash were applied. One week to 10 d after stubble incorporation,

Effect of stubble incorporation on N application and grain yield, Coimbatore, India.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	
	Summer 1982-83	Summer 1983-84
Recommended dose (100-22-42 kg NPK/ha)	5.2	6.5
15-cm stubble + 25% N	4.3	5.1
30-cm stubble + 25% N	3.2	5.2
45-cm stubble + 25% N	4.0	5.0
15-cm stubble + 50% N	3.8	5.0
30-cm stubble + 50% N	5.0	5.2
45-cm stubble + 50% N	5.4	6.6
15-cm stubble + 75% N	4.4	5.6
30-cm stubble + 75% N	4.4	5.3
15 cm stubble + 15% N	4.1	5.8
CD	0.6	0.7

the field was plowed again, leveled, and the second rice crop planted. Results showed that with stubble incorporation chemical N application could be reduced without yield loss (see table).

In both years, 45-cm-tall stubble with 50% of the normal N fertilizer yielded highest among treatments and at par with the recommended application of 100-22-42 kg NPK/ha. □

Response of lowland rice to fertilizer application

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Often, a rice crop does not yield well even after liberal application of NPK. Next to N,

P deficiency can be a major constraint to yield. Experiments to identify reasons for low yield indicate Zn deficiency limits rice production in Punjab. S deficiency can also be a constraint.

We studied the response of rice to balanced nutrient application based on general recommendations and soil analysis

Soil characteristics of fields at experiment sites in Punjab, India.

Site	Texture	pH	E. C. (mmho/cm)	Organic carbon (%)	Available p ^a (kg/ha)	Available K ^b (kg/ha)
1	Sandy loam	8.7	0.20	0.48	7.5	465
2	Sandy loam	9.0	0.30	0.38	10.0	450
3	Sandy loam	9.0	0.30	0.33	10.0	420
4	Sandy loam	9.2	0.30	0.21	10.0	412
5	Sandy loam	8.8	0.30	0.45	12.5	262

^aDetermined in Olsen's extract (0.5 N NaHCO₃ solution: pH 8.5). ^bExtracted with neutral normal ammonium acetate solution.

Grain yield (t/ha)

Response of rice to fertilizers (mean of 5 sites).

at five sites in farmer fields in Punjab. NPK was applied at 120-13-24 kg/ha, based on the general recommendation. When fertilizer application was based on soil analysis, 25% more N and P and 25% less K were applied, except at site 5 (see table). Soils were deficient in DTPA extractable Zn and 10 kg Zn/ha was applied. Soils were medium-textured and alkaline

with low electrical conductivity, organic carbon, and available P and high available potash.

Data in the figure show the yield differences obtained by applying N, NP, NPK, and NPKZn. Application of NP increased yield 1.4 t/ha (30%) than applying N alone. Soils with P deficiency responded significantly to P application. Response to

applied K was small. When 50 kg ZnSO₄/ha + NPK were applied, yield increased 0.6 t/ha (12%) over yield with NPK alone.

Our research showed that applying only N fertilizer is not sufficient to maximize rice yield. A balanced application of nutrients, including Zn and S, based on soil analysis, results in optimum yield. □

Rice-Based Cropping Systems

Rice and air-breathing fish culture: effects of seasonal variations on the yields of grain, straw, and fish

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We studied the effects of seasonal variations on the yields of mixed cultures of air-breathing catfish Singhi (*Heteropnaustes fossilis*) and Magur (*Clarias batrachus*) and high yielding rices at ORP in pre-kharif (Mar-Jun), kharif (Jun-Nov), and boro (Nov-Apr) rice seasons. Rices Ratna, Pankaj, and Jaya were grown.

Experiments consisted of a control treatment of rice without fish and plots of rice with air-breathing fish. Plots were 35 × 10 m with a shallow 75- × 40-cm-perimeter canal, bounded by a dike. Equal numbers of Magur and Singhi fingerlings were stocked at 1 fish/m² 7 d after transplanting. Before stocking, they were

Effects of seasonal variations on the yield of grain, straw, and fish at ORP, Pandua, West Bengal, 1983-84.

Yield factor	Yield (t/ha)					
	Prekharif (Ratna)		Kharif (Pankaj)		Boro (Jaya)	
	Without fish	With fish	Without fish	With fish	Without fish	With fish
Grain	3.2	3.8	3.0	3.1	5.9	6.4
Straw	8.1	8.1	8.9	9.7	5.0	5.8
Fish	—	0.4	—	0.4	—	0.5

treated with a 100 ppm solution of formalin for 30 s. Each morning, fish were fed a low-cost 1:2 mixture of fishmeal and rice bran mixed with cowdung at 5% body weight. Fish were harvested with rice by draining the plots.

Soil was a clay loam with pH 6.5-7.0. Farmyard manure at 9 t/ha was applied to all plots during land preparation. The plots were plowed and 100 kg N/ha was applied: 1/2 at land preparation and 1/2 in equal splits 1 mo after transplanting and 1 wk before flowering. PK at 18-33 kg/ha was applied during tillage. Seedlings at 2/hill were transplanted at 15- × 15-cm spacing.

Standard cultivation methods were practiced and field water level was maintained at 8-10 cm. Plankton consisted mainly of *Spirogyra*, *Volvox*, *Ulothrix*, *Euglena*, *Pinularia*, *Monia*, *Cyclops*, *Keratella*, and *Brachionus*.

Combined rice and fish culture produced best in all seasons. Grain and fish yield were maximum in boro followed by pre-kharif and kharif (see table). Straw yield was maximum in kharif. Of the three varieties, Jaya performed best.

Stem borer population was highest in the control and least in rice-fish plots. □

Announcements

Meelu elected to ARRW Executive Committee

O. P. Meelu, senior research fellow, Multiple Cropping Department, IRRI, was elected Councilor (North Zone) to the Association of Rice Research

Workers of the Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, India, for 1984 and 1985. Meelu is actively engaged in research on fertilizer efficiency in rice and rice-based cropping sequences at Punjab Agricultural University. □

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